

IJCRSS

**International Journal of
Contemporary Research in
Social Science
Volume 2 Number 2
August 2015**

ISSN 2349-0195

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IJCRSS

(International Journal of Contemporary Research in Social Science)

A Peer reviewed Quarterly Journal

ISSN: 2349 – 0195

Volume 2, Issue 2

August 2015

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GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF E-COMMERCE IN INDIA

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Abstract

Over the last decade, the Internet has changed the way people buy and sell goods and services. Online retail e-commerce is transforming the shopping experience of customers. The sector has seen unprecedented growth especially in the last two years. The adoption of technology is enabling the e-commerce sector to be more reachable and efficient. Devices like smartphones, tablets and technologies like 3G, 4G, Wi-Fi and high-speed broadband is helping to increase the number of online customers. Banks and other player's in-commerce ecosystem are providing a secured online platform to pay effortlessly via payments gateways. The homegrown players have shown tremendous growth and attracted some big investors. The entry of global biggies like Amazon and Alibaba has taken the competition to a new level. E-tailors are differentiating themselves by providing innovative service offerings like one-day delivery, 30-day replacement warranty, cash on delivery (Cod), cash back offers, mobile wallets, etc. The supply chain has improved significantly and e-tailors' are even leveraging on the services of Indian Post for greater

Reach across the country. This paper discusses the e-commerce market growth and its advantages.

Key words – *e-commerce, e-tailing, India, Internet, Development.*

Objectives of the Study

- ❖ To analyze the present trends of E-commerce in India;
- ❖ To examine the technologies helped in E-commerce in India;
- ❖ To describe the present status and future of E-commerce in India.

Introduction

The technology driven e-commerce market in India has come of age and is growing rapidly. The digital commerce market is set to cross Rs.1 lakh crore by December 2015 from Rs.81, 525 crore in December 2014, with 53 percent growth," Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI) represents digital businesses across the country and address challenges facing the industry, including mobile content and services. The Indian Market Research Bureau's (IMRB) the latest "Digital Commerce" reports, Segments such as travel, e-tailing, financial services, matrimony and classifieds have leveraged upon the technology to drive e-commerce across the country. "Online travel has emerged as the largest segment in terms of revenue generation, followed by online retail, mainly driven by cash-on-delivery, which accounts for about 50 percent of its sales,". Though financial services segment is a late entrant in the digital world, it has shown an upward growth due to growing awareness and trust on online transactions. "Classifieds and other services like online entertainment ticketing and food/grocery ordering were, however, early entrants in the e-commerce space," In transactions too, the travel segment has been a driving force for the growth of the e-commerce industry in the country. "Online travel by internet users accounted for 61 percent or Rs.50, 050 crore of the digital transactions in 2014," Of the non-travel transactions that contributed to the remaining 29 percent or Rs.31, 245 crore in value, e-tailing accounted for 76 percent or Rs.24, 046 crore, financial services 14 percent (Rs.4, 508 crore), matrimony and classified 3 percent (Rs.896 crore) and other services 6 percent (Rs.2, 025 crore). "The non-travel industry segment is expected to touch Rs.50,000-crore mark by December, 2015. Mobile phones and phone accessories contributed 41 percent (Rs.9,936 crore) to the e-tailing segment, followed

by apparel, footwear and personal items, which generated 20 percent (Rs.4,699 crore). Consumer durables and kitchen appliances contributed 14 percent (Rs.3,404 crore) while laptops/net books/tablets, home furnishings and books generated Rs.2,780 crore, Rs.1,059 crore and Rs.648 crore, respectively. Also found that about 46 percent of online shoppers prefer cash on delivery as a mode of payment, while 21 percent prefer payment through debit card and 16 percent via credit card and Net banking, mobile wallets contributes 17 percent.

Indian e-commerce Scenario

Indian digital commerce space is fast growing. One big reason is the prominent shift to internet, via Smartphones, Tablets and/or Laptops. According to the report by Mobile Internet in India 2014, India will soon reach the mark of 213 million mobile internet users by June 2015, indicating a jump of 23% in a time span of 6 months (January 2015-June 2015). The consumer mentality of Indian customers is changing fast, aiding to the growth of this industry. This high-end growth can be attributed to few recent facts

- ❖ Low priced smartphones and 2G/3G/4G networks has enabled internet access everywhere, even in the rural areas. Tier II and Tier III cities are growing fast.
- ❖ Rise of the middle class people, who have less time. They are more prone to do everything on their smartphones, even shopping.
- ❖ Free home Delivery, deals, discounts, and offers of such have given a boost to this industry.
- ❖ Increase in the use of Mobile wallets.
- ❖ With people using technology to shop, more online retail stores are opening up, making way for more employment.

Services provided under the various modes of e-commerce

E-Commerce transactions can be segmented into three broad categories or modes, based on participants involved in the transaction.

Business-to-Consumer (B2C) the B2C market in India generates the bulk of revenues across the consumer-facing modes of e-commerce. Furthermore, though online travel has typically held a major share of the B2C market, online retail is also growing rapidly and is expected to significantly increase its share.

Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C) India's C2C market, though currently small, is set to grow with the entry of several players. These entrants are attracting investment. Their online portals are also garnering significant traffic. We expect the C2C segment to show rapid growth in coming years.

Business-to-Business (B2B) the most common users of B2B online classifieds are micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs). These small businesses lack the requisite financial resources and, therefore, find it difficult to market their products and services to potential clients through traditional media such as newspapers, banners and television. Trade through online B2B portals increases the visibility of MSMEs in the marketplace and helps them overcome barriers of time, communication and geography.

Investments in e-commerce companies from 2014-2015

The latest numbers from Ministry of Statistics have shown India is to take a lead in terms of the fastest growing economy, beating out China next year. Economic status of the country is evolving and, as a result, e-commerce industry is heading north without any traces of slowing down. Investors prefer e-commerce companies in India to invest their money. In the food retail industry, Big Basket, a leading grocery retail store received \$32.7 million in September 2014 from Helion Ventures, Ascent Capital, Zodiuss Capital and Lion rock Capital. In order to maintain their grounds, big daddies of e-commerce are indulging into acquisitions. For instance, leading fashion retailer, Myntra that reportedly has 60 percent of its sales happening from mobiles. Similarly, baby care retailer Babyboy, that had acquired its competitor Hoopoes in late 2013, itself got acquired by Mahindra groups in February 2015. However, with Flipkart, Amazon taking up the maximum market, most of the player in baby care section has faded with time. Currently, only Hopscotch and First Cry have managed to survive. One of the recent

investments to happen in 2015 is that of Quikr. An online classifieds platform has very recently entered the billion dollar club after it received a funding of \$150 million from new investor Stead view Capital along with existing investors Tiger Global and eBay. The startup is now valued at \$1 billion.

Key Development in e- commerce in India

FIG – 2 INTERNET USERS BY COUNTRY: IN MILLION (2014)

Source: Internet Live Stats website, December 2014.

- ❖ It is evident that in absolute terms India’s internet users are shorty only 36 million as compared with 279 million in the US and higher than that in Japan, Brazil and Russia. However, in relation with its population, only 19% Indians uses the internet. This indicates the potential of internet use in India and as internet penetration increases, the potential of growth for the e-commerce industry will also increase.
- ❖ Key developments in 2014 Mobile to be the most influential aspect of e-commerce with mobile apps being developed by most e-commerce websites, smartphones are increasingly replacing PCs for online shopping. In 2013, only 10 percent of the mobile user’s used smartphones, and only 5 percent of the e-commerce transactions were made through a mobile device. This figure has more than doubled and more than 13 percent of all e-commerce transactions today happen via mobile. According to some industry players, over 50 percent of the orders are being placed through mobile apps, which is not only leading to substantial customer acquisition but also building customer loyalty for various brands. However, most mobile transactions so far are for entertainment, such as booking movie tickets and music downloads. This trend will change soon with more and more merchandise being ordered online.

More business coming from smaller town e-commerce is increasingly attracting customers from Tier 2 and 3 cities, where people have limited access to brands but have high aspirations. According to e-commerce companies, these cities have seen a 30 percent to 50 percent rise in transactions. Enhanced shopping experience besides general online shopping, customers are also shopping online for weddings and festivals. The free and quick shipment and wider choice of products, along with the ease of shopping online as compared to in-store shopping, is also helping e-commerce gather momentum. Further, e-commerce companies are doing rapid business due to sales. New concepts such as sales on

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weekends, holidays and festivals are attracting a lot of new customers and building customer loyalty among existing customers. Television and social media, particularly Facebook, are playing a proactive role in promoting e-Tailing through aggressive advertisements. This has helped several e-commerce companies build substantial brand image.

Market Size of Indian e-commerce

The digital commerce market in India has grown steadily from \$4.4 billion in 2010 to \$13.6 billion in 2014. As per industry estimates, the digital commerce market in India is expected to reach \$16 billion by the end of 2015 on the back of growing Internet population and increased online shoppers. Online travel accounts for nearly 61 percent of e-commerce business while e-tailing contributes about 29 percent.

FIGURE - 3 ONLINE RETAIL IN INDIA - MARKET SIZE (\$ BILLION)

Source: IAMA, Deloitte Analysis

Business Models in E-commerce

E-commerce market in India has started to become crowded and complex with several players fighting for a fair share of customers' mind and wallet. As the competition in the e-commerce heats up, the companies are using multiple business models in order to get customer attention including:

- ❖ Inventory model e.g. Shopper Stop, Croma
- ❖ Social networks e.g. TripAdvisor
- ❖ Aggregator Model e.g. Ola Cabs
- ❖ e-Marketplace e.g. Flip kart, Snap deal
- ❖ Transaction broker e.g. IRCTC
- ❖ Click and Collect service e.g. Amazon

To survive and sustain operations in the competitive market, companies are also taking advantage of one or multiple revenue models including:

- ❖ Advertising revenue model e.g. Yahoo.com
- ❖ Subscription revenue model e.g. Flint box
- ❖ Transaction fee model e.g. eBay
- ❖ Sales revenue model e.g. Amazon

- ❖ Affiliate revenue model e.g. CouponDunia

Opportunities and Challenges of e-commerce in India

Enabling Technologies The greater adoption of Internet and smartphones is the biggest driver of e-commerce in India. Internet penetration is rapidly increasing with around 300million users in 2014. The smartphone is steadily growing and consists of 35% of the overall mobile phones market in the country. 7 The success rate of some of the technologies is directly connected to the success of e-commerce.

Cloud Technology Most of the e-toilers are depending on cloud technology for its flexibility, scalability, availability, mobility, and efficiency. Cloud communications can be an important enabler in helping e-commerce companies in ensuring personalized consumer engagement throughout the purchase cycle and also in executing effective and near real-time marketing campaigns.

Mobile Applications More than 235 million people in India access internet through mobile devices. This is the primary reason for e-toilers to focus their efforts on mobile app penetration across the country. The mobile applications are helping to reach more customers located even in remote and rural areas. E-commerce companies have been able to bridge the service gap considerably by sending service updates and other communication via their mobile app, e-mail, and SMS.

Digital Advertisements The digital advertisement industry is growing rapidly as there is a growth in digital communication device around the world. The increase in smartphones, tablets is enabling advertisers to reach a wider audience. The digital advertisements are flexible and can be adapted for any kind of device like Television, laptop, tablet, or smartphone. The two -way interactive capability and the ability to customize the ad for target audience also make digital advertisements more effective.

Search Engine Optimization (SEO) With thousands of products in the digital catalogues, the e-commerce players find it easy to be visible with the help of SEO technology. SEO can help the websites to be more specific, measurable, realistic, and time efficient and hence can significantly boost profits. E-tailors' should optimize the critical aspects of their online store and earn rich snippet displays in search results on various search engines to drive more targeted, motivated buyers to their products. Though the e-commerce sector is growing exponentially in India, it faces several challenges like customer mindset, high cash on delivery (Cod) based orders, reach ability, poor courier services and other policy-related issues.

High competition there are several players doing the same business in almost the same way. Within tense competition the profitability is decreasing dueto aggressive pricing strategies, heavy discounts and offers, free delivery, high commissions to affiliates and vendors during sale period to name a few.

Poor logistic & supply chains E-commerce companies live on the reach and the ability to stock more items than physical stores as these are their biggest differentiators. With this benefit also comes the challenge of robust supply chains and logistics networks, which are not comparable and developed to global standards in India. The courier companies do not have nationwide delivery networks and also do not have the skills of handling commercial value goods. They also do not have the skills for handling Cod; recheck return parcels, and other complexities related to digital sale. This is forcing several e-tailors' to establish their own delivery network across the country and might have to engage with multiple shipping methods using FedEx or DHL for the last mile delivery.

Payments E-commerce companies have to offer a wide variety of payment options including CoD, credit and debit card, and internet banking, among others. More than 50 percent of the payments are made using the CoD option in India as customers fear to share information online and do not trust the website for secure payments. Moreover, the return percentage of orders in CoD is much higher compared to online payments. To counter these fears, e-tailers have started to provide facility of paying with Card on Delivery. For example, Amazon's delivery person brings point-of-sale device to accept payment at customer premise.

Future of E-commerce in India

Another trend that is fast growing to dominate in the e-Commerce industry is that of social shopping. It means shoppers' friends can indulge in shopping experience. At present India has only two players in this area- Lime road and Xara to, who have integrated social shopping with online product discovery. Last year Gartner Inc. had estimated E-commerce market in India worth \$6 billion in 2015, projecting a 70 percent growth from 2014 revenue of \$3.5 billion. However, according to the latest report by IAMAI and IMRB International, the Indian e-Commerce industry is expected to grow at a rate of 33 percent and cross INR one lakh crore (US\$16.3 billion) by the end of 2015. With the way people are getting dependent on their smartphones and the rapid penetration of internet, e-commerce is definitely the future of India.

Conclusion

E-commerce is dynamic and is throwing up new business models at a fast pace. It is imperative that tax laws/ administration keep pace meeting the challenges posed by such models to ensure appropriate taxation. In 2014, Indian Post collected ` 2.8 billion through CoD option of payment. India slipped from 14th to 20th rank among the top 30 developing countries in 2014 Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) that looks at measures for retail investments worldwide. Chile and China are leading in the GRDI rankings. The sector is still in its growth stage in India and has enormous potential to offer in the coming years. The government's most prestigious Digital India project could take the sector to new heights. It is necessary to adopt global taxation principles for e-commerce which would form the cornerstone of a country's national tax regime to deal with e-commerce scenarios. The borderless nature of e-commerce calls for a coordinated effort at the international level to result in a level-playing field for multi-national companies in all countries. The role of government is to provide a legal framework for e-commerce so that while domestic and international trade are allowed to expand their horizons, basic rights such as privacy, intellectual property, prevention of fraud, consumer protection etc. are all taken care of.

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